

INTEGRATION OF SHALAWAT IN ISLAMIC BOARDING SCHOOL EDUCATION MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: The phenomenon of the integration of prayer in the management of Islamic boarding school education is an important topic to study in the context of the development of religious culture and spiritual leadership in Islamic educational institutions. This study aims to explore how the integration of prayer can build religious culture and spiritual leadership in Islamic boarding schools. A qualitative approach with a case study method is used to explore this phenomenon. Data were collected through in-depth interviews, participatory observations, and documentation in several Islamic boarding schools in Madura, East Java. The results of the study show that shalawat plays a significant role in the daily life of students and the management of Islamic boarding schools. The integration of prayer helps create a religious atmosphere, improve student discipline, and strengthen spiritual leadership in Islamic boarding schools. The implication of this study is the importance of adopting the integration of prayer as a managerial strategy in pesantren education to form religious character and effective leadership. Moreover, French-language Algerian literature, born from the writing models adopted in the French school during colonization, would gradually move away from them to create its own literary field with new values as well as different aesthetic categories.

Keywords: Shalawat, Religious Culture, Spiritual Leadership

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Introduction

The phenomenon of the integration of prayer in the management of Islamic boarding school education is an interesting and relevant topic to be researched in the context of the development of religious culture and spiritual leadership in Islamic educational institutions. (Yani et al., 2021). Shalawat, as a form of praise and prayer to the Prophet Muhammad SAW, has an important position in the Islamic tradition and is often an integral part of religious practices in Islamic boarding schools. Islamic boarding schools, as traditional Islamic educational institutions, have a strategic role in shaping the character and spirituality of students. Therefore, it is important to examine how the integration of prayer can strengthen religious culture and spiritual leadership in Islamic boarding schools.

The academic relevance of this topic can be seen from several points of view. First, the integration of shalawat in pesantren education management can provide new insights into spiritual-based learning methods that can improve the quality of education and character formation. (Sholikhin, 2023). Second, this research can also contribute to the spiritual leadership literature by providing empirical evidence on how religious practices such as prayer can affect leadership styles and management effectiveness in Islamic boarding schools. Third, in a social

context, the integration of prayer can be seen as an effort to maintain and strengthen religious cultural identity in the face of modernization and globalization.

The theories behind this research include transformational leadership theory and spiritual-based learning theory (Anthony & Hermans, 2020; Prabhu & Koodamara, 2021). The theory of transformational leadership, developed by James MacGregor Burns and Bernard Bass, states that transformational leaders are those who are able to inspire and motivate their followers to achieve higher goals through a clear vision and mission. In the context of Islamic boarding schools, leaders who often integrate prayer into daily activities can be considered transformational leaders who inspire students to get closer to Allah and follow the example of the Prophet PBUH.

The main problem that this research focuses on is how the integration of prayer in pesantren education management can build religious culture and spiritual leadership. Although many Islamic boarding schools have implemented the practice of prayer in their daily activities, there are still few studies that have deeply examined the impact of such integration on the development of religious culture and spiritual leadership in Islamic boarding schools. One of the heads of the pesantren said, "We routinely read the shalawat, but there has not been an in-depth study of how this affects the leadership and culture in the pesantren." This shows the need to explore further the role of prayer in forming a religious and spiritually led pesantren environment.

Previous research that is relevant to this topic includes studies by (Irawati et al., 2023; Islam et al., 2021; Jankowski et al., 2022) Which examines the influence of religious practices on spiritual leadership in Islamic schools in Malaysia. The results of this study show that religious practices, including the recitation of shalawat, have a positive correlation with effective spiritual leadership. Furthermore, research by (Hidayat & Hidayat, 2023; Purwanto et al., 2021) Revealed that the integration of prayer in the pesantren curriculum can improve the discipline and motivation of students. This research emphasizes the importance of spiritual aspects in the learning process to achieve optimal results. In addition, a study by (Asrop et al., 2022; Kaputra et al., 2022; Syaie, 2022) highlighting how shalawat can be used as a tool to build identity and solidarity among students, which in turn strengthens religious culture in Islamic boarding schools.

Although these studies provide valuable insights into the role of shalawat in Islamic education, there are still research gaps that need to be explored. Most of the previous research focused more on the practical aspects of the recitation of prayer and its impact on individual students, while the impact of the integration of prayer on educational management and spiritual leadership in Islamic boarding schools has not been studied in depth. Therefore, this study seeks to fill the gap by exploring how shalawat can be systematically integrated into the management of pesantren education and how this affects culture and leadership in the pesantren environment.

The novelty of this study lies in its holistic and systematic approach to examining the integration of prayer in pesantren education management. This research not only sees shalawat as a routine religious practice but also as a managerial instrument that can shape organizational culture and spiritual leadership. This approach makes a new contribution to the Islamic education management literature by providing a model of prayer integration that can be adopted by other Islamic boarding schools. In addition, this study also provides practical insights for pesantren leaders on how to implement shalawat in their management strategies to achieve more holistic educational goals.

This research aims to explore and understand how the integration of prayer in pesantren education management can build religious culture and spiritual leadership. Specifically, this

study aims to: (1) identify the strategy of integrating prayer in daily activities in Islamic boarding schools, (2) analyze the impact of prayer integration on religious culture in Islamic boarding schools, and (3) evaluate how the practice of prayer affects spiritual leadership in Islamic boarding schools. By achieving this goal, the research is expected to make a meaningful contribution to the development of a pesantren education management model based on spiritual and religious values

Methods

This study uses a qualitative approach with a case study type of research. The qualitative approach was chosen because the purpose of this research is to understand the phenomenon of shalawat integration in pesantren education management in depth and context. (Chanifah et al., 2021; Prayogi et al., 2022). Case studies are used because this research is focused on one unit of analysis, namely pesantren, which allows researchers to explore the phenomenon in more detail. This research was conducted in several Islamic boarding schools located in Malang, East Java, including the Nurul Huda Islamic Boarding School, which is located in Kembang Jeruk Village, Banyuwates District, Sampang Regency, East Java 69263, and the Miftahul Ulum Islamic Boarding School, which is Tlambah Village, Karang Penang, Sampang, East Java 65149.

The data collection techniques used in this study include in-depth interviews, participatory observations, and documentation. In-depth interviews were conducted with pesantren leaders, teachers, and students to get diverse perspectives on the practice and influence of shalawat in pesantren life. Participatory observation is carried out by participating in various activities involving the recitation of shalawat, both in daily routine activities and special events, to understand the context and its application directly. Documentation is carried out by collecting data from the pesantren archives, including curriculum, activity schedules, and student achievement records. The data triangulation technique is applied to ensure the validity and reliability of the data obtained.

The data analysis technique used in this study is thematic analysis. The data obtained from interviews, observations, and documentation were analyzed through several stages, namely transcription, coding, and theme retrieval. Transcription is carried out to convert oral data from interviews into written form. Coding is done by providing code on important parts of the transcription and observation notes that are relevant to the purpose of the research. After that, the themes that emerge from the coding are analyzed to find patterns and relationships between them. The results of this thematic analysis are then used to answer research questions and draw conclusions about the integration of prayer in the management of Islamic boarding school education and its impact on religious culture and spiritual leadership

Result and Discussion

إِنَّ اللَّهَ وَمَلَائِكَتَهُ يُصَلُّونَ عَلَى النَّبِيِّ يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا صَلُّوا عَلَيْهِ وَسَلِّمُوا تَسْلِيمًا

It means "Indeed, Allah and His angels pray for the Prophet. O you who believe, pray for the Prophet and pay homage to him."

Through this piece of verse, this study aims to understand how the integration of prayer in the management of Islamic boarding school education can build religious culture and spiritual leadership. (Nazirwan et al., 2020). Based on the results of interviews and observations in various Islamic boarding schools, it was found that prayer plays a significant role in the daily life of students and the management of Islamic boarding schools.

Shalawat as an Instrument of Strengthening Religious Culture

Islamic boarding schools that consistently integrate prayer in daily activities and special events tend to have a higher level of solemnity among students. (Dwi et al., 2024). This is because

shalawat helps create an atmosphere full of majesty and solemnity, which in turn increases the discipline and commitment of students to Islamic values. Thus, prayer plays an important role in shaping the religious character of students and creating a harmonious pesantren environment and full of spiritual values.

Shalawat is integrated into various aspects of pesantren life, both in routine activities and special events. One of the caregivers of the pesantren stated,

"Shalawat is an integral part of our pesantren life, every morning and evening students are obliged to recite shalawat together (I_Kyai_2024)."

This statement shows that shalawat is not only practiced individually but also collectively, creating a deeply religious atmosphere in the pesantren environment. The integration of prayer in daily activities such as tadarus Al-Qur'an and dhikr together strengthens the spiritual values of students and forms a solid religious character. The results of observation showed that pesantren who routinely held prayer readings had a higher level of solemnity among students compared to those who did not.

Prayer and Spiritual Leadership

Spiritual leadership in Islamic boarding schools is greatly influenced by the practice of shalawat. One of the pesantren administrators said,

"By reading the prayer frequently, we hope to emulate the noble qualities of the Prophet PBUH in our leadership (I_PP_2024)."

This practice helps pesantren administrators to be closer to Islamic values and apply them in management. Observations show that pesantren leaders who are active in the practice of prayer are more respected by students and staff because they are considered to have high spirituality and good example. This creates a harmonious environment and increases the compliance and motivation of students in participating in pesantren activities.

Integration of Shalawat in Curriculum and Extracurricular

The integration of prayer in the curriculum and extracurricular activities is one of the main strategies in pesantren education management. An Ustadz stated,

"We teach shalawat not only as a recitation but also to understand its meaning and apply it in daily life (I_U_2024)."

The curriculum that integrates prayer helps students understand the importance of prayer in a broader context, namely as a means of getting closer to Allah and His Messenger. This is reinforced by a snippet of a verse from the Qur'an

لَا يُكَلِّفُ اللَّهُ نَفْسًا إِلَّا وُسْعَهَا ۗ أَلْهَآ مَا كَسَبَتْ وَعَلَيْهَا مَا اكْتَسَبَتْ

It means "Allah does not burden a person but according to his ability. He gets the reward (of virtue) that he pursues and he gets the punishment (of evil) that he does."

According to the interpretation of the Qurtubi, this verse teaches that Allah does not impose a burden that exceeds the ability of His servants. It covers all aspects of life, including worship and social responsibility. (Aly & Bustomi, 2022).

Through the routine practice of shalawat, students are taught about the importance of commitment and discipline in carrying out worship. (Saridudin & Munawiroh, 2021), which ultimately forms a strong and formidable character according to their respective abilities. In addition, extracurricular activities such as prayer reading competitions and hadron groups are also a medium to express students' love for the Prophet PBUH. Data shows that students who are active in prayer activities have better academic and non-academic achievements, because they are more motivated and have high spiritual discipline.

The Impact of Shalawat on Discipline and Ethics of Students

The practice of prayer regularly also has a positive impact on the discipline and ethics of students. A student revealed,

"Every time we read shalawat, we feel calmer and motivated to follow the rules of the Islamic boarding school (I_S_2024)."

This statement reflects that prayer has a calming psychological effect, thus helping students to be more disciplined and obey the rules. In addition, the integration of prayer in character education makes students appreciate the values of honesty, humility, and responsibility more. (AchmadKurniady & Rosalin, 2021; Islahiyah et al., 2023). The following table shows the relationship between the frequency of prayer recitation and the level of discipline of students:

Table 1. The relationship between the frequency of prayer recitation and the level of discipline of students

Frequency of Prayer Recitation	Level of Discipline of Students
Every day	Highly disciplined
3-4 times a week	Discipline
1-2 times a week	Lack of discipline
Infrequently	Undisciplined

From the table, it can be seen that the more often students read shalawat, the higher the level of discipline. This shows a positive correlation between the practice of prayer and the disciplined behavior of students.

Shalawat as a Shaper of Islamic Boarding School Identity

قال رسول الله صلى الله عليه وسلم: "من صلى عليّ صلاةً صلى الله عليه بها عشراً." (رواه مسلم)

Meaning "The Prophet Muhammad PBUH said: "Whoever prays to me once, Allah will pray to him ten times." (HR. Muslim)."

This hadith strengthens the motivation of students to regularly pray. In addition to getting rewards, prayer is also a means to get closer to Allah and increase love for the Prophet PBUH. (Kumaini & Yasinta, 2021). This practice also helps in the development of better spiritual character of students. In addition, Shalawat is also an identity that distinguishes one pesantren from another. One of the heads of the Board of Directors said,

"Shalawat is a characteristic of our pesantren, every guest who comes is always impressed by the solemnity of the students when reading the prayer (I_KP_2024)."

The integration of prayer in the identity of the pesantren creates a peculiarity that is not only known internally but also externally. This helps the pesantren in building its reputation and attracting the interest of prospective students and parents. The following graph shows the level of parental satisfaction with the integration of prayer in Islamic boarding schools:

Graph 1. Level of Parental Satisfaction with the Integration of Shalawat in Islamic Boarding Schools

From the graph, it can be seen that the majority of parents are very satisfied with the integration of prayer in Islamic boarding schools, with the main reason being the formation of religious character and the improvement of the spirituality of students.

Conclusion

This study shows that shalawat plays a significant role in the daily life of students and the management of Islamic boarding schools. The integration of prayer in various daily activities and special events at Islamic boarding schools contributes to increasing the solemnity, discipline, and commitment of students to Islamic values. The practice of prayer that is carried out collectively not only strengthens the religious character of students but also creates a harmonious atmosphere full of spiritual values. In addition, the positive influence of prayer on the spiritual leadership of Islamic boarding schools can be seen from the higher respect and example for leaders who are active in this practice, as well as the improvement of discipline and ethics among students.

For further research, it is recommended to further explore the specific impact of different types of prayer on certain aspects of pesantren life, such as the development of student character, leadership effectiveness, and interpersonal relationships in the pesantren environment. Comparative research between Islamic boarding schools that have different frequencies and methods of prayer recitation will also provide more in-depth insight into best practices in the integration of shalawat. In addition, a longitudinal analysis of the long-term influence of the integration of shalawat on the spiritual and academic development of students can help to understand the ongoing impact of this practice on the life of the pesantren

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